

Figure S1. Overall diversity of the datasets at the class taxonomic level. (A) Distribution of taxa abundance in each dataset demonstrating a high proportion of 'microbial dark matter' present in the metagenomic and metatranscriptomic datasets. (B) Hub network at the class level, hub size indicates hub score, with one being highest hub score and zero being lowest. Each network represents the three types of data depicting the distinctive patterns of unknown organisms, labeled as 'microbial dark matter', within the microbialite communities.

Figure S2. Overall diversity of the datasets at the order taxonomic level. (A) Distribution of taxa abundance in each dataset demonstrating a high proportion of microbial dark matter present in the metagenomic and metatranscriptomic datasets. (B) Hub network at the order level, hub size indicates hub score, with one being highest hub score and zero being lowest. Each network represents the three types of data depicting the distinctive patterns of unknown organisms, labeled as ‘microbial dark matter’, within the microbialite communities.

Figure S3. Overall diversity of the datasets at the family taxonomic level. (A) Distribution of taxa abundance in each dataset demonstrating a high proportion of microbial dark matter present in the metagenomic and metatranscriptomic datasets. (B) Hub network at the family level, hub size indicates hub score, with one being highest hub score and zero being lowest. Each network represents the three types of data depicting the distinctive patterns of unknown organisms, labeled as ‘microbial dark matter’, within the microbialite communities.

Figure S4. Overall diversity of the datasets at the genus taxonomic level. (A) Distribution of taxa abundance in each dataset demonstrating a high proportion of microbial dark matter present in the metagenomic and metatranscriptomic datasets. (B) Hub network at the genus level, hub size indicates hub score, with one being highest hub score and zero being lowest. Each network represents the three types of data depicting the distinctive patterns of unknown organisms, labeled as ‘microbial dark matter’, within the microbialite communities.

Figure S5. Venn diagram of microbial dark matter shared amongst the amplicon (A), metagenome (MG) and metatranscriptome (MT) datasets at all taxonomic levels.

Figure S6. Networks created at the phyla level for amplicon, metagenome and metatranscriptome datasets showing structural changes in network connectivity when comparing networks created with and without microbial dark matter (MDM).

Figure S7. Networks created at the class level for amplicon, metagenome and metatranscriptome datasets showing structural changes in network connectivity when comparing networks created with and without microbial dark matter (MDM).

Figure S8. Networks created at the order level for amplicon, metagenome and metatranscriptome datasets showing structural changes in network connectivity when comparing networks created with and without microbial dark matter (MDM).

Figure S9. Networks created at the family level for amplicon, metagenome and metatranscriptome datasets showing structural changes in network connectivity when comparing networks created with and without microbial dark matter (MDM).

Figure S10. Networks created at the genus level for amplicon, metagenome and metatranscriptome datasets showing structural changes in network connectivity when comparing networks created with and without microbial dark matter (MDM).

Figure S11. Comparison of centrality scores for the amplicon dataset between the original network (green), the network without unknown taxa (orange) and the bootstrap network at all taxonomic levels (yellow). The evaluated network metrics of the hubs represent connectivity including betweenness centrality, closeness centrality and co-occurrence (i.e., degree centrality) (ns, $p > 0.05$; *, $p \leq 0.05$; **, $p \leq 0.01$; ***, $p \leq 0.001$; ****, $p \leq 0.0001$).

Figure S12. Comparison of centrality scores for the metagenomic dataset between the original network (green), the network without unknown taxa (orange) and the bootstrap network at all taxonomic levels (yellow). The evaluated network metrics of the hubs represent connectivity including betweenness centrality, closeness centrality and co-occurrence (i.e., degree centrality) (ns, $p > 0.05$; *, $p \leq 0.05$; **, $p \leq 0.01$; ***, $p \leq 0.001$; ****, $p \leq 0.0001$).

Figure S13. Comparison of centrality scores for the metatranscriptomic dataset between the original network (green), the network without unknown taxa (orange) and the bootstrap network at all taxonomic levels (yellow). The evaluated network metrics of the hubs represent connectivity including betweenness centrality, closeness centrality and co-occurrence (i.e., degree centrality) (ns, $p > 0.05$; *, $p \leq 0.05$; ** $p \leq 0.01$; ***, $p \leq 0.001$; ****, $p \leq 0.0001$).

Figure S14. Bar plots indicating microbial diversity at the class level for top 20 hubs in the presence (+) and absence (-) of microbial dark matter in the amplicon (A), metagenome (MG) and metatranscriptome (MT) datasets.

Figure S15. Bar plots indicating microbial diversity at the order level for top 20 hubs in the presence (+) and absence (-) of microbial dark matter in the amplicon (A), metagenome (MG) and metatranscriptome (MT) datasets.

Figure S16. Bar plots indicating microbial diversity at the family level for top 20 hubs in the presence (+) and absence (-) of microbial dark matter in the amplicon (A), metagenome (MG) and metatranscriptome (MT) datasets.